

Entropy for a Plane Wave and for the Bohm Aharonov Effect

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In a previous note (1), we discussed writing Shannon's entropy using $P(p/x)P(x) = W^*(x) a(p) \exp(ipx)$ as the probability instead of the usual $P(x)$. Thus, one has $-W^*(x)W(x) \ln[W(x) + W^*(x) \sum_p a(p) a^*(p) \ln[a(p)]]$ where b is a constant related to the normalization of $\exp(ikx)$ as a basis function. This differs from the usual: $W^*(x)W(x) \ln[W^*(x)W(x)]$. Thus, a plane wave $\exp(ikx)$ has a nonzero entropy, it seems, using this alternative entropy form. This suggests the plane wave interacts with the vacuum and $\exp(i k x)$ represents an average motion with k being an average momentum. This is in keeping with ideas of (2) for which a particle in a box with infinite potential walls has a wavefunction $B \sin(kx)$, but k represents the average momentum. All momentum plane waves $\exp(ipx)$ are stirred up. In a previous note (3), we argued that a free particle with momentum k would have different phases while traveling through constant potentials $V1$ and $V2$ (where there is no force). In this note, we try to calculate the entropy for a plane wave. We argue that the different phases represent different microscopic interactions with the different potentials or vacuum in the case of no potential. In addition, we argue that these same ideas apply to the Bohm-Aharonov case. There is no force, but there is an electromagnetic potential $A(x)$ in space which adds a phase to the free plane wave. This too should have its own entropy value if microscopic coupling occurs between the $\exp(ipx)$ Fourier pieces of $\exp(i k ave x)$ and the momentum dependent potential and with the Fourier pieces of $\exp(i e/hbar c \int_{x1=0}^x A(x1) dx1)$.

Entropy

Traditionally, Shannon's entropy is given by $-W^*(x)W(x) \ln[W^*(x)W(x)]$ ((1)) based on a probability $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$. If one uses $P(p/x)P(x)$, one may obtain an alternative Shannon's entropy given by:

$$\sum_x \{-W^*(x)W(x) + W^*(x) \sum_p a(p) a^*(p) \ln[a(p)]\} + \sum_p b a(p) a^*(p) \ln[|a(p)|] \quad ((2))$$

where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$.

It should be noted that traditional entropy yields 0 for a plane wave $\exp(i px)$. In (3), we argued that a particle with momentum p traveling through a constant potential $V1$ acquires a different phase than if the particle with p traveled through $V2$ and think that as a result there should be different entropies for these cases.

Entropy for a Plane Wave

In this note, we consider the general plane wave $\exp(-ikx)$. Here $-k$ may represent the momentum in a vacuum, or include a potential related phase shift if the particle travels through

a region with a constant potential V_i . Thus, the objective is to find the entropy ((2)) for a plane wave which traditionally would be zero using ((1)).

From ((2)), $-W^*(x)W(x) \ln(W(x)) = ikx$ and $W^*(x) \times d/dx W(x) = -i xk$ so these two cancel.

Thus, the entropy calculation is based on: $\sum_{p \in \mathbb{R}} a(p) a^*(p) \ln(|a(p)|)$ ((3))

For a plane wave created at a point $x=0$, $W(x)=0$ for $x<0$ and $W(x)=\exp(-ikx)$ for $x \geq 0$. Thus, there is a step function which affects the Fourier transform, causing all momentum $\exp(ipx)$ terms to appear. In particular, the Fourier transform $a(p) = 1/[i(k+p)]$ where $-k$ is the average momentum. (The Fourier transform is taken from (4).)

Thus, ((3)) in 1-dimension becomes: $M = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dp \frac{1}{(k+p)^2} \ln(|k+p|)$ where the integration limits are from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$ in keeping with (2) and b is a constant related to the normalization of $\exp(ikx)$ as a basis function. Using integration by parts:

$\int \frac{1}{x^2} \ln(x) dx = -\ln(x)/x$ evaluated at endpoints $- 1/x$ evaluated at endpoints

We write M as: $\int_{p=-k}^{\infty} \frac{1}{[(p+k)(k+p)]} \ln(p+k) + \int_{p=-\infty}^{-k} \frac{1}{[(k+p)(k+p)]} \ln(|p+k|)$

$\int_{p=-k}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(p+k)(k+p)} \ln(p+k) = \ln(p+k)/(p+k)$ at $p=k + 1/(p+k)$ Using l'Hopital's rule this equals 0.

$\int_{p=-\infty}^{-k} \frac{d(p+k) \ln(|k+p|)}{[(k+p)(k+p)]}$ $k+p < 0$ so $y = -(k+p) > 0$
The integral equals $[-\ln(k)/k - 1/k]$

Thus, the overall entropy for a plane wave with momentum $-k$ is using ((2)) is:

$$\text{Entropy} = b(-\ln(k)/k - 1/k) \quad ((4))$$

Here $-k$ is the average momentum for a wave moving in a region with no potential. If there is a constant potential V_i and this causes a phase shift of $C(i)x$ then $k = \text{free momentum} + C(i)$. Thus, a particle moving through one V_i would have a different entropy than one moving through a region with a different V_i .

If one uses $\exp(ikx)$ as the plane wave i.e. k and not $-k$ is the average momentum, then one may write:

$$M = \int_{p=k}^{\infty} dp \frac{1}{[(p-k)(p-k)]} \ln(p-k) + \int_{p=-\infty}^k dp \frac{1}{[(k-p)(k-p)]} \ln(|-k+p|)$$

The first integral again leads to 0 for the same reasons as given above.

For $B = \int_{p=-\infty}^k d(p-k) \frac{1}{[(k-p)(k+p)]} \ln(|-k+p|) \quad -k+p < 0 \text{ so } y = -(-k+p) > 0$

$B = - \int_{p=0}^k dy \frac{1}{(y^*y)} \ln(y) = -\ln(k)/k - 1/k$ with the other terms cancelling using l'Hopital's rule.

Thus, this approach also yields: Entropy = $b[-\ln(k)/k - 1/k]$

Bohm-Aharonov Case

We argue that for the Bohm-Aharonov case, there should also be an entropy because the phase shift indicates an interaction between the particle and potential $A(x)$, both kinetically and through the "overall potential" $(e/cA)(e/cA)^{1/2m} - 1/m e/c A d/dx W$. To calculate this, we again use ((2)).

$$-W^*W \ln(W) = -i[k + ie/\hbar c \int_{x_1=0, x} A(x_1) dx_1]$$

$$W^* x d/dx W = xi [k + ie/\hbar c \int_{x_1=0, x} A(x_1) dx_1]$$

Thus, the first two terms again cancel and it is again:

Sum over p $b a(p) a^*(p) \ln(|a(p)|)$ ((5)) which yields the entropy.

$a(p)$ must be calculated using an explicit function for $A(x)$ i.e.

$$a(p) = \int_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \exp(ikx) \exp(ie/\hbar c \int_{x_1=0}^x A(x_1) dx_1) \exp(-ikx) \quad ((6))$$

This may then be used in ((5)), but an integral will need to be performed. The point we wish to make is that we believe that having a phase shift may lead to a different entropy for a plane wave than for the case in which there is no phase shift or a different phase shift. Thus, the Bohm-Aharonov case will have its own entropy value.

Conclusion

In this note, we try to argue that using the expression ((2)) for entropy, a plane wave has an entropy which we calculate as $b[-\ln(k)/k - 1/k]$ where k is the average momentum. Thus, we argue that a plane wave interacts with a vacuum and $\exp(i kx)$ only represents average motion with k being an average momentum. If there is a constant potential present or if one has the Bohm-Aharonov case, the interactions are with the given potentials and the entropy may be

different. Ultimately, we try to argue that different plane waves or plane waves with a phase shift have an entropy and that this entropy should differ for the different cases.

References

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